

The value of industrial attachments to Library and Information Science Students at Mzuzu University

Lombani Gondwe

Department of Information Sciences, Mzuzu University

August 2025

Abstract

This study investigated the value of industrial attachments to Library and Information Science (LIS) students at Mzuzu University. Industrial attachments are intended to prepare Library and Information Science (LIS) students at Mzuzu University for professional practice by linking classroom knowledge with work place experience. However, their effectiveness has been questioned due to challenges such as inadequate resources, weak supervision and limited opportunities to apply LIS specific skills about their true value. In examining potential solutions this study has discovered areas where institutions can make advances in industrial attachments. The objectives of the study were to identify the skills gained, the benefits, and the challenges faced by LIS students during their industrial attachments. The research employed a quantitative approach, using a survey design. Data was collected from 69 students in the 2023 and 2024 cohorts through questionnaires, and was analysed using SPSS version 19 to generate frequencies, percentages, and tables.

Findings of the study showed that students gained a wide range of skills, with the most common being cataloguing and classification, customer service and user support, use of library management systems such as KOHA, information retrieval, and teamwork. Students reported high confidence in applying these skills in future careers. The main benefits highlighted were exposure to real library operations, personal growth and confidence, networking with professionals, and improved job readiness. However, the study also revealed challenges. Personal challenges included financial difficulties, health issues, and lack of confidence. Institutional challenges included limited access to resources, being assigned irrelevant tasks, inadequate supervision, and restricted opportunities to practice LIS-specific skills. The study concluded that industrial attachments are valuable in equipping LIS students with both technical and soft skills necessary for employability and career development. However, to maximise their effectiveness, challenges must be addressed. The study recommends enhanced supervision, adequate resource provision, pre-attachment preparation, and

longer placement periods. The findings provide insights that can inform curriculum improvement, policy formulation, and stronger collaboration between universities and host institutions.

Keywords

Industrial attachments, Mzuzu University, Library and Information Science

Introduction

One of the main goals of higher education is to prepare graduates toward their respective careers. Marciniak et al. (2022) describe the concept of career preparedness as the attitudes, knowledge, competencies and behaviours necessary to deal with expected and unexpected career transitions and changes. There is a need to prepare graduates in ensuring that they are equipped with the right skills to tackle the challenges and take advantage of the opportunities that the future holds (Baynit & Ngussa, 2021). With an array of training methodologies available in higher education institutions, the Industrial Attachment Programme (IAP) is gaining momentum over others and is becoming an inevitable training methodology (Dondofema et al., 2020). Therefore, industrial attachment approach has been established in an attempt to make higher learning relevant and meaningful to students and the community. The approach is being applied at various levels of education including higher learning institutions.

Industrial attachments refer to an academic course which students in training are posted to institutions, organisations, or industries by the department/institution offering a programme of study in order to have hands-on experience related to the career being pursued (Fajonyomi et al., 2024). A number of terms which include an internship, practicum, work-related learning, are used interchangeably with industrial attachment (Bruce & Dewah, 2018). It can either be paid or unpaid. It is offered in order to gain work experience or satisfy requirements for a qualification obtainable from a training institution. These industrial attachment positions are usually temporary. Generally industrial attachments consist of an exchange of services for experience between the student and the organisation (Maseka, 2020).

In Library and Information Science (LIS), industrial attachments are considered as a skilled development exposure, as a form of experiential learning, without which participation in the

national and international labour force will be low (Bird et al., 2015). This study intended to study the value of industrial attachments to library and information science at Mzuzu university.

Contextual setting

Mzuzu University is the second public university after the University of Malawi. It was enacted by an Act of Parliament of Malawi in May 1997 and was officially opened in 1999 (Mzuzu University, 2025). This idea was conceived by the government in 1994 to increase access to higher education and contribute to the nation's future through education, training and research (Mzuzu University, 2025). Since its first intake in 1999, the university has gradually grown from a single faculty to six faculties, and is currently offering 33 undergraduate programmes and 20 postgraduate programmes (Mzuzu University, 2025). Mzuzu University's vision is to be a premier provider of tertiary education, research, and outreach in Malawi and the world and its mission is to provide high-quality education, training, research and complementary services to meet the technological, social and economic needs of individuals and communities in Malawi and the world (Mzuzu University, 2025). Most of the programmes require students to pursue an industrial attachment course for a specified period of time and the Library and Information Science (LIS) programme is not an exception. The main objective of attachment for LIS students is to match the students' educational goals with community and organisation needs; and to provide students with practical experiences which reinforce their academic learning (Maseka, 2020).

The Department of Information Sciences formerly the Department of Library and Information Science sits within the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences and traces its origins to 2003 (Mzuzu University, 2025). The department adopted its current name in 2016 to reflect a broader, digitally oriented scope. The department emphasises training professionals who can manage, organise, and use information for societal development, offering programmes such as the Bachelors and Master's degree in Library and Information Science (Mzuzu University, 2025). Within the undergraduate Bachelor of Library and Information Science (BLIS) programme, industrial attachment is included as a compulsory course in the curriculum. It is taken during the fourth year of study and is formally assessed like any other course unit. The Department sends its students for placement with various organisations and institutions such as the National Archives of Malawi, Domasi College of Education, and University of Malawi among others. Students are assessed and at the end of the industrial attachment period, they submit their reports for examination to the host organisation and the industrial supervisors. Their scores from these reports and supervision are considered as part of students' grades for the award of their degrees.

Statement of the problem

Industrial attachments serve as exposure to the real work environment so that the student can relate theories learned in class and apply them in the workplace to prepare them for their future career as professional librarians (Khamis & Kaur, 2023). The attachments should provide workplace experience that requires the student to practically do the task and be able to apply their knowledge in the library setting. Regardless of the prominence of industrial attachment as a cardinal part of the tertiary education, there have been concerns such as lack of adequate resources like well-equipped libraries/information related settings, limited Information and Communication Technology (ICT) resources by students and institutions. Studies on industrial attachments highlight both benefits and challenges for students. For example, Acheampong et al. (2015) found that students are placed in industries for attachments just to meet curriculum requirements. However, students often feel used as cheap labour by industries. They also raise concerns about the type of work they are given, the length of the attachment, and the timing of the program.

Bruce and Dewah (2018) and (Khamis & Kaur, 2023) highlight a gap between academic training and industry expectations in applying classroom knowledge in real-world settings, which creates a mismatch in organisations. According to Norina et al. (2015), employers and academic researchers had identified gaps between corporate needs and graduates' attributes which indicated that graduates had little real-world experience, lacked communication, teamwork and problem-solving skills as well as having poor working attitudes. These studies reveal a broader concern about the inadequacy of industrial attachments training and academic programs in preparing students for the demands of the job market. There is a need to help students move from the "book and theories" to the "real clients and real work places" (Wilson, 2016).

At Mzuzu University, LIS students are required to undertake industrial attachments in various institutions to gain practical experience. However, despite their intended benefits, some factors reduce their effectiveness, raising concerns about how well they prepare students for future job opportunities. The researcher inquired from some students who have completed their attachments and shared their experiences. Some said lack of adequate resources like well-equipped libraries, limited information and communication technology resources hindered them from fully gaining meaningful hands-on experience from their industrial attachments.

Others mentioned that they were lacking professional guidance, making their learning experience inconsistent and less useful. These raise concerns about the value of industrial attachments as they hinder their professional competencies. Notwithstanding the above, little is known on how industrial attachments impact LIS students at Mzuzu university. This study therefore aimed to address this gap by investigating the value of industrial attachments to LIS students at Mzuzu University.

Literature review

Skills obtained during industrial attachments

A mixed methods study by Bird et al. (2015) studied industrial attachments in LIS education: An international perspective on experiential learning in Australia and Belgium, results from questionnaires and interviews revealed that hands-on experiences cultivate critical skills among students such as problem-solving, digital archiving, teamwork, and reflective practice. Students reported enhanced ability to confront real-world challenges, bridging theoretical concepts from classrooms with library-specific workflows.

Similarly, Yesmin (2025) conducted a mixed study of LIS industrial attachments programs in Bangladesh. Their findings from questionnaires and interviews indicate that students gained significant hands-on skills in areas such as cataloguing, classification, library automation, digital repositories, and virtual information services. Moreover, the industrial attachments fostered the development of soft skills such as communication, professionalism, and workplace ethics.

Importantly, the study highlighted the importance of structured supervision and alignment between institutional goals and internship activities, factors that ensured students maximized learning during their industrial placement.

A qualitative study by Raszewski and Peterson (2020) studied Benefits of a joint health sciences practicum for students in library and information sciences in the United States. Results from interviews showed that students gained skills from exposure to multiple workflows, subject guide development, and database management skills that proved advantageous even outside health library contexts.

Another qualitative study by Cooper (2015) at Queens College in New York studied student reflections on LIS industrial attachments from a service learning perspective supporting multiple

learning theories. Findings from interviews with 14 students revealed that they gained communication skills (both oral and written), problem-solving skills (for example resolving user queries, fixing cataloguing errors, or managing unexpected challenges in service delivery), collaboration and team work where many students worked alongside professional librarians, learning the value of team collaboration.

A qualitative study by Khan (2022), on towards developing library and information science practicum supervision competency framework in North America, Europe and Asia . Although the focus was on supervision, the study identified key student skills fostered during these practicum experiences. The findings from semi-structured interviews with 43 participants that included library and information science professionals and students showed that students gained curriculum alignment and planning where students gained an understanding of how to integrate academic knowledge into practical tasks, reflection and critical thinking, service and user engagement skills, where students engaged with users through guided supervision, gaining insight into user-centred service practices; and digital utilisation tools where they adopted the use of technologies such as digital cataloguing systems and e-resources under practicum supervision.

In Africa, a qualitative study by Magara (2025) in Uganda examined how LIS interns from Makerere University's East African School of Library & Information Science (EASLIS) applied their academic training in real-world government offices. This qualitative case study involved self-administered questionnaires and interviews with interns and field supervisors.

Findings showed that, as a result of this practicum training, students gained a significant deal of experience in several aspects of information management and technology. Students also learned teamwork, clients handling and public relations skills, customer care, and minutes and report writing. Students also reported that they have acquired communication skills, interpersonal relationship skills, records and information management skills, word processing skills, etc, and made new friends. A mixed methods study by Munyoro and Mutula (2016) investigated LIS education and employability in Zimbabwe. Although the focus was on employees and employers, the study identified key student skills that gained during industrial attachments. The findings from interviews and questionnaires showed that LIS students gain employability skills from industrial attachments before getting employed, they include, ability to use and apply information technology

in library, ability to translate print-based services to electronic services able to communicate and train or teach, able to work as a team, negotiate, work with diversity.

Studies reviewed above demonstrate availability of literature on the skills obtained during industrial attachments. However, the only known study in Malawi by Chaputula (2014) at Mzuzu University which addressed the skills of LIS graduates in their job prospects and not on skills obtained during industrial attachments to LIS students. This gap necessitated the study.

Benefits of industrial attachments

Library and information science (LIS) literature relevant to industrial attachments has addressed benefits of industrial attachments. A quantitative study by Duffus (2017) in the university libraries at University of North Carolina (UNC), North Carolina in America assessed the benefits of industrial attachments to LIS students. Results from questionnaires revealed that students benefited strong professional development. Students improved their confidence in delivering reference services, learned how to teach library instruction sessions, and became more comfortable interacting with real patrons. They also gained mentorship, resume feedback, and job interview preparation, which contributed to higher job readiness and employability.

A quantitative study by Juznic and Pymm (2015) in Slovenia and Australia conducted a comparative study on students placements in academic/research libraries. The findings from questionnaires showed that students reported the following, enhanced job readiness and cataloguing proficiency, stronger reflective skills and professional self-awareness and Stronger reflective skills and professional self-awareness.

A qualitative study by Burns (2024) explored how Library and Information Science (LIS) students in Malaysia participated in community-based learning during their industrial training. The findings from Semi-structured interviews showed that practical experience enhanced student learning beyond routine technical work, they were able to led outreach programs in communities.

In Africa, a quantitative study by Inyang and Okwueze (2024) in South-South Nigeria revealed that participation in the Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) significantly improved LIS students' skills in information consultancy and repackaging. The research emphasises that hands-on training is very important for learning these skills and advised students to do their industrial attachments in places where they can get a lot of practical experience.

A mixed method study by Maseka, (2020) at University Zambia on LIS students revealed that students benefited from industrial attachments the results from questionnaires and interviews in the study revealed that Students acquired knowledge on how to manage database and performing reception duties in the library and also their knowledge were broadened their ICT skills and helped them work with electronic information in the library. Others benefited on Librarian to client relationship skills and how to handle client complaints and acquired knowledge on library cataloguing, reference, archiving books and collection development. Students also learnt how to catalogue and classify books and finally they have knowledge on electronic reference skills. This revealed that many benefited a lot on acquisition of knowledge and how to manage database and they really appreciated the importance of industrial attachment that is put in place by the school for student to have experience of job-related idea. The study finding also showed that majority of the students said that participation in the LIS industrial attachments opened new experiences for them as undergraduates and broadened their future employment possibilities.

A review paper by Dondofema et al. (2020) in Zimbabwe reviewed the history, benefits, and challenges of industrial attachment programs in Zimbabwe. The results showed that industrial attachments are vital for students to gain real-world experience, develop professional networks, and improve their employability. The authors recommended that institutions should establish clear policies and provide adequate support to maximize the benefits of industrial attachments.

The studies above indicate different benefits of LIS industrial attachments in various countries/universities. The only known study in Malawi at Mzuzu University by Chipeta and Chawinga (2018) which addressed LIS graduates' career path, and find out the relevance of their educational attainment to their present careers, and to examine their perceptions about the LIS curriculum not benefits of industrial attachments to LIS students. Hence the study wants to study the benefits of industrial attachments to LIS student.

Challenges during industrial attachments

In India a mixed study by Pandey and Kumar, (2020) investigated perceived impact of LIS industrial attachments programme on personal and professional competencies of students of Banaras Hindu university. The results from 172 out 260 questionnaires, literature review and records of the department of library and information science showed that students expressed concerns about inadequate time allocated to industrial attachments, insufficient hands-on experience with

specialized software, and lack of structured mentorship and professional development sessions. In India, a quantitative study by Sarkar and Nand kishore (2024) analysed challenges and opportunities in library and information science education In West Bengal focusing on industrial attachments. The findings from the questionnaires showed that students expressed concerns about lack of technology exposure (weak access to specialized software and digital systems), limited practical time and mentorship gaps (Few structured guidance sessions and follow-ups).

In Africa, a study by Ojokuku et al. (2015) in Nigeria examined the influence of students' industrial work experience scheme on professional development of library and information science students in south-west, Nigeria from 3 universities, results from 221 questionnaires revealed that most students met the following challenges during industrial attachments transport, accommodation, inadequate finance and inability to secure places of training, on supervision of the trainees, majority of LIS students asserted that supervision was inadequate.

A mixed study by Kavulya (2017) in Kenya to assess training of library and information science (LIS) professionals in Kenya: A needs assessment. The findings from questionnaires with open and close ended questions, interviews and document reviews pointed the following challenges of industrial attachments: short placement duration, limited ICT integration, and lack of up-to-date library systems during the placement period.

A review paper by Dondofema et al. (2020) in Zimbabwe on industrial attachments across tertiary programs including LIS used a systematic literature review. The findings pointed out widespread difficulties for students: limited placement spots, misaligned tasks, employers unwilling to provide real training, and supervision that was weak or unfocused on learning.

Studies reviewed above demonstrate availability of literature on challenges faced by LIS students during industrial attachments. There is no known study in Malawi at Mzuzu University about challenges of industrial attachments to LIS students. This gap was the reason for doing this study.

Methodology

This study was conducted at Mzuzu University. The study employed a quantitative research method and survey research design because it allowed the researcher to collect data from large group of students about their skills and experiences regarding industrial attachments. The study did not use any sampling technique instead it used a census, this was because the researcher

intended to include all students of class of 2025 and class of 2024 in the survey study. The target population for the study was 79, those who conducted their attachments in 2023 and 2024.

Data was collected from 69 student using structured questionnaires with a mix of open-ended and closed-ended questions. Questionnaire was used because they are handy in reaching individuals dispersed across wide geographical areas or residing in remote locations, as it was with the target population in this study also, respondents also enjoy the flexibility to complete postal questionnaires in their own time, with the added convenience of scheduling telephone call-backs (Kuphanga, 2024). In this study ethical clearance was obtained from department of Information Sciences at Mzuzu University in order to administer questionnaires. Confidentiality of the information given by the respondents was assured to all respondents. Ethical issues were put in place in this study by seeking permission from all participants included before embarking on the study. Furthermore, all participants were assured of anonymity in their participation in the study and that the study was purely for academic purposes. In addition, all participants were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and used only for this study and the data collected was kept confidential after analysing results using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 19.

Findings

Background characteristics of respondents

Results in table 1 show that more males participated in the study with a score of 36 (52%) than females 33 (48%). The majority of the respondents are in the age range of 21-29 with a score of 44 (64%). In terms of year of attendance many attended their attachments in 2024 with a score of 42(61%).

Table 1: Background characteristics of respondents

Characteristics		n=69	%
Gender	Male	36	52
	Female	33	48
Age range	20 and below	1	1
	21-29	44	64
	30-39	4	6
Year	2024	42	61
	2023	27	39

Skills obtained during industrial attachments

Table 1 show that 58 (84%) indicated customer service and user support; 57 (83%) students indicated cataloguing and classification skills; 50 (72%) indicated use of library management system (e.g. KOHA); 48 (70%) indicated communication and team work; 41 (59%) indicated information retrieval skill; 37 (54%) indicated report writing and documentation; 35 (51%) indicated managing electronic resources and database; 22 (32%) indicated digital archiving; 22 (32%) indicated organising and running library events and programs; one (1%) specified critical thinking skill; one (1%) collection development, skill and emergency remedies in library; one (1%) specified personal organisation (being punctual and dressing well); one (1%) specified that they gained user orientation skills. Therefore, these findings reveal that the majority of the students acquired the skills in cataloguing and classification, information retrieval and customer service and user support from the industrial attachments.

Table 2: skills obtained during industrial attachments n=69

Skills Obtained During Attachments	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Customer service and user support	58	84
Cataloguing and classification	57	83
Use of library management system e.g KOHA	50	72
communication and team work	48	70
Information retrieval	41	59
Report writing and documentation	37	54
Managing electronic resources and database	35	51
Digital archiving	22	32
Organising and running library events and programs	22	32
Critical thinking	1	1
Collection development	1	1
Emergency remedies in Library	1	1
Personal organisation (being punctual and dressing well)	1	1
Books acquisition, managing children corner and orientation	1	1

Note: multiple responses were received

ways of acquiring skills and level of confidence

The study asked respondents to indicate how they acquired the skills and their level of confidence in applying learned skills in future opportunities. Results are presented in Table 2. Table 2 shows that 55 (80%) students acquired the skills through hands on practice; 43 (62%) acquired the skills through mentor guidance at the place of attachment; 41 (59%) students acquired the skills through observation of staff members; 29 (42%) students acquired the skills through formal training; 28 (41%) students acquired the skills through self-learning (manuals and online resources); and only one (1%) students indicated that they were utilising their skills learnt in class; and one other (1) students indicated that they acquired the skills through attending training sessions and meetings. Therefore, the study found that the majority of students who attended industrial attachments acquired their skills through hands on practice, observation of staff members at the place of

attachment, and through mentor guidance from their supervisors. The majority graded their level of confidence as very high with a score of 35 (51%); 30 (43%) graded their confidence as high; 2 (3%) as moderate; one (1%) as low and one (1%) as very low.

Table 3: ways of acquiring skills and level of confidence

Ways of acquiring skills and level of confidence		n=69	%
Ways of acquiring skills	Hands on practice	55	80
	Mentor guidance	43	62
	Observation	41	59
	Formal training	29	42
	Self-learning	28	41
	Utilising skills learnt in class	1	1
	Attending training sessions	1	1
Level of confidence	Very high	35	51
	High	43	43
	Moderate	3	3
	Low	1	1
	Very low	1	1

Note: multiple responses were received

Benefits of industrial attachments their opportunities and application of classroom knowledge

The findings in Table 3 show that 54 (78 %) students were exposed to real library operations; 44 (64%), students benefited personal growth and confidence; 40 (58%) students benefited from networking with professionals; 38 (55%) students improved job readiness; and only one (1%) student specified that placements helped them to boost their career.

The results suggest that the majority of students were exposed to real library operations, and also developed their personal growth and confidence. The study solicited data on new opportunities

met during industrial attachments. Results presented in Table 3 shows that 40 (58%) students had an opportunity to network with LIS professionals; 25 (36%) students had an opportunity to attend internship at the host institution; 7 (10%) students had an opportunity to get employed by the host institution; and one (1%) indicated that they were given an opportunity to showcase what was learnt in class. The results suggest that the majority of students had an opportunity to network with LIS professionals and opportunity to attend internship at the host institution. The study collected data on whether if the industrial attachments helped respondents to apply classroom knowledge in real word setting. respondents were asked to indicate the level of agreement among the options strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. Findings presented in Table 3 shows that 36 (52%) students strongly agreed; 28 (41%) students agreed, three (4%) students were neutral on the matter; and two (3%) students disagreed. The findings reveal that the majority of the students strongly agreed that the industrial attachments helped respondents to apply classroom knowledge in real word setting. This suggest that industrial attachments helped many to apply classroom knowledge.

Table 3: benefits, opportunities and application of classroom knowledge

Benefits, opportunities and application of classroom knowledge		n=69	%
Benefits	Exposure to real library operations	54	78
	Personal growth and confidence	44	64
	Networking with LIS professionals	40	58
	Improved job readiness	38	55
	Career development	1	1
Opportunities	Opportunity to network with LIS professionals	40	58
	Opportunity to attend internship at the host institution	25	36
	Opportunity to get employed by the host institution	7	10
	Opportunity to show case what was learnt in class	1	1
Application of classroom knowledge	Strongly agree	36	52
	Agree	40	41
	Neutral	3	4
	Disagree	2	3

Note: multiple responses were received

Challenges faced during industrial attachments

Findings presented in Table 4 show that 50 (72%) students faced financial constraints during their industrial attachments; eight (6%) were lacking confidence in performing assigned tasks and four (8%), had personal challenges such as health. the results suggest that many faced financial constraints during their industrial attachments. The study solicited data on institutional challenges. Findings presented in Table 4 Show that 20 (29%) faced lack of resources like computers; 17 (27%) faced being given irrelevant/repetitive tasks; 17 (25%) indicated limited opportunity to practice LIS specific skills; 6 (9%) faced poor communication; 4 (6%) indicated host not aligned with LIS;

1(%) indicated that that there was no room for innovations; 1(%) indicated that there is a need for more for industrial attachments. The results suggest that many faced inadequate access to resources at the host institution.

Challenges		n=69	%
Personal challenges	Financial challenges	50	72
	Lack of confidence in performing assigned tasks	8	12
	Health	4	6
Host institution challenges	Inadequate access to resources (eg computers)	20	29
	Being given irrelevant/repetitive tasks	17	27
	Limited opportunity to practice LIS specific skills	17	27
	Lack of supervision	10	14
	Poor communication from the host	6	9
	Host not aligned with LIS	4	6
	No room for innovation	1	1
	More time for industrial attachments	1	1

Note: multiple responses were received

Discussion of findings

Skills obtained during industrial attachments

The findings of the study reveal that industrial attachments significantly contribute to the development of both technical and soft skills among Library and Information Science (LIS) students at Mzuzu University. This is the case since the students are accorded the opportunity to learn the skills and at the same time practice them within the industry from experts who have much experience on their job.

Other moderately reported skills were report writing and documentation, managing electronic resources and database, Organising and running library events and programs and digital archiving.

A small number of respondents each also indicated acquisition of other skills such as critical thinking, collection development, user orientation, emergency remedies in libraries, personal organisation, and managing children's corners.

The findings are consistent with existing literature across multiple regions. For instance, a large-scale mixed-method study by Bird et al. (2015) which studied LIS industrial attachments in Belgium and Australia, reported that practical placements cultivated essential skills such as problem-solving, digital archiving, teamwork, and reflective practice skills also identified by students in this study. Similarly, the high percentage of students reporting cataloguing and classification skills aligns with the findings of Yesmin (2025) who found that LIS students in Bangladesh gained strong practical abilities in cataloguing, classification, and automation through industrial attachment.

Moreover, the high frequency of students gaining customer service and user support skills and communication and teamwork supports the findings of Cooper (2015) whose qualitative study revealed that students developed communication, problem-solving, and collaboration skills through working alongside professionals during service delivery. Likewise, Khan (2022) emphasised that LIS students under structured supervision gained exposure to user engagement practices, digital tools, and reflective learning, which resemble with the findings in this study.

Further supporting these results is a study by Magara, (2025) in Uganda, where students reported acquiring communication, report writing, customer care, and interpersonal relationship skills many of which were also cited by Mzuzu University students. Munyoro and Mutula, (2016) similarly concluded that LIS students in Zimbabwe developed employability skills such as teamwork, ICT application in libraries, communication, and adaptation to digital services during their attachments. While fewer respondents in this study reported skills such as digital archiving and report writing compared to other skills, these still align with the findings seen in Bird et al., (2015) and Magara (2025), indicating that while these skills may be less emphasised at some attachment sites, they remain core competencies gained through practicum experience, apart from skills listed in existing literature the study also found additional skills including; critical thinking, Personal

organisation (being punctual and dressing well), collection development and Managing children corner and orientation.

Benefit gained during industrial attachments

The findings from this study indicate that industrial attachments offer multiple benefits to Library and Information Science (LIS) students at Mzuzu University. The most frequently cited benefit was exposure to real library operations. This was followed by personal growth and confidence, networking with professionals, and improved job readiness. One respondent additionally indicated that the placement contributed to career development.

These findings are similar with existing studies across various regions. For example, a study by Duffus (2017) in the United States at the University Libraries at UNC–Greensboro found that LIS students gained strong professional development through their placements. The study also reported improvements in confidence, delivery of reference services, teaching library instruction sessions, and increased comfort in engaging with real patrons closely aligned with the benefits reported by students at Mzuzu University.

Supporting these results is a comparative study by Juznic and Pymm (2015) in Slovenia and Australia, which revealed that placements enhanced job readiness, reflective skills, and professional self-awareness. These benefits closely relate the present study's findings on improved job readiness and personal growth among LIS students. In Malaysia, similarly Burns (2024) in Malaysia found that industrial attachment expanded student learning beyond technical work, allowing them to lead outreach initiatives and engage more fully in the library profession. The current study also reflects this, particularly in how students reported personal confidence and professional networking. Moreover, in Africa Inyang and Okwueze (2024) reported in Nigeria that participation in industrial attachments improved LIS students' skills in consultancy and repackaging of information, stressing the value of hands-on training a view echoed by respondents in this study who reported real-world exposure and job readiness gains. Furthermore, a review paper by Dondofema et al. (2020) emphasised the importance of attachments in Zimbabwe, citing real-world experience, professional networking, and enhanced employability. These points strongly correspond with the benefits identified by the majority of respondents in this study.

Challenges met during industrial attachments

Personal challenges

The most prevalent personal challenge, reported by of respondents, was financial constraints, particularly in areas such as accommodation and transport. Other challenges included health-related issues, limited placement duration and lack of confidence in performing assigned tasks. These findings indicate that the cost of participating in industrial attachments presents a significant barrier to students and may affect their ability to fully engage with their placement experience.

These findings are in line with studies across different regions. For example, Ojokuku et al. (2015) in Nigeria found that financial constraints, including transport and accommodation, were among the leading personal challenges faced by LIS students during industrial attachment. Similarly, Kavulya (2017) in Kenya identified short placement durations and inadequate infrastructure as constraints to effective student learning. The study also found health related challenges apart from those in literature.

Institutional challenges

In terms of challenges from host institutions, the most reported issues were inadequate access to resources such as computers, being given irrelevant or repetitive tasks, and limited opportunity to practice LIS-specific skills. Additional challenges included lack of supervision, poor communication, host institutions not aligned with LIS, and lack of room for innovation.

The issue of insufficient supervision and misalignment with LIS objectives also echoes findings from global literature. Pandey and Kumar (2020) in India found that students frequently encountered limited access to specialized tools, inadequate mentorship, and insufficient structured development sessions. Likewise, Sarkar and Nand kishore (2024) highlighted lack of technology exposure and mentorship gaps as common students concerns during attachments in West Bengal. Dondofema et al. (2020) in Zimbabwe noted that students across multiple tertiary programs, including LIS, often faced systemic institutional issues such as misaligned tasks, lack of training opportunities, and weak supervision issues clearly mirrored in the Mzuzu University context. apart from challenges the existing literature the study also found other challenges such as lack of room for innovation and limited time for industrial attachment.

This study also adds new knowledge specific to the Malawian context. Unlike existing research in other countries, no prior study had documented the challenges faced by LIS students at Mzuzu

University during industrial attachments. The gap in local literature on this issue was a key motivation for conducting the present study.

Conclusion

The general conclusion is that industrial attachments are vital in equipping LIS students at Mzuzu University with both technical and soft skills, enhancing job readiness, and providing valuable professional exposure. However, to maximize their effectiveness, both academic institutions and host organizations must address the challenges identified in this study.

The study found that the most acquired skills during industrial attachments include customer service and user support, cataloguing and classification, use of library management systems such as KOHA, communication and teamwork, and information retrieval, moderately acquired skills include: report writing and documentation, managing electronic resources and database and digital archiving. The study also found acquisition of other skills which include: critical thinking, collection development, user orientation, emergency remedies in libraries, personal organisation, and managing children's corners. The skills were acquired through acquired through observation of staff members, through hands on practice, through formal training, mentor guidance, through self-learning, by utilising skills learnt in class, through attending training sessions and meetings. It was revealed that students had higher level of confidence in applying these skills in future opportunities.

The study found that industrial attachments offer multiple benefits to Library and Information Science (LIS) students at Mzuzu University. The most frequently cited benefit was exposure to real library operation, personal growth and confidence, networking with professionals and improved job readiness, additionally placement contributed to career development.

The study found that students face personal challenges and institutional challenges during their industrial attachments. Personal challenges include; financial constraints, particularly in areas such as accommodation and transport. Other challenges included health-related issues and lack of confidence in performing assigned tasks. Institution challenges include inadequate access to resources such as computers, being given irrelevant or repetitive tasks, and limited opportunity to practice LIS-specific skills, lack of supervision, poor communication, host institutions not aligned with LIS, and lack of room for innovation.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the study makes the following recommendations:

- Prepare students adequately before placement by conducting pre attachments orientation and practical sessions on core skills. This should be conducted by department of LIS.
- Encourage innovation and creativity by allowing students to contribute ideas and engage in reflective learning, instead of treating them only as assistants. This should be done by both department of LIS and the host institutions.
- Extending duration to ensure that students get more time to engage meaning fully to LIS specific skills.
- Improve supervision and mentorship especially in the host institutions.
- Facilitate access to essential resources such as computers, library systems, and cataloguing tools to allow students to practice real-world LIS skills.

References

- Acheampong, E., Samoah, A., Williams, A., & Azu, T. D. (2015). Industrial attachment: perspectives, conceptions and misconceptions of students at Cape Coast Polytechnic, Ghana. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(35).
- Adam, A. M. (2020). Sample size determination in survey research. *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jsrr/2020/v26i530263>
- Ahmed, S. K. (2024). How to choose a sampling technique and determine sample size for research: A simplified guide for researchers. *Oral Oncology Reports*, 12, 100662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oor.2024.100662>
- Alem, D., D. (2020). An overview of data analysis and interpretations in research. *International Journal of Academic. Research and Education Review*, 8(1), 1–27. <https://dSoi.org/10.14662/IJARER2020.015>
- Alvi, M., H. (2016). *A manual for selecting sampling techniques in research*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303941309>
- Asio, J. M. (2021). research designs in the new normal: A brief overview. *Academia Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.20935/al2596>
- Baynit, M., & Ngussa, B., M. (2021). Effect of field attachment experiences on students' career preparedness in higher learning institutions: A case of selected universities in Arusha. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review*, 8(5), 182–191. <https://doi.org/10.15739/IJEPRR.21.020>

- Bird, N. J., Chu, C. M., & Oguz, F. (2015). Internship in LIS education: An international perspective on experiential learning. *IFLA Journal*, 41(4), 298–307. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0340035215596352>
- Bruce, K., N., & Dewah, P. (2018). *The value of industrial attachment to the archives and records management students at the National University of Science and Technology in Zimbabwe*. 51.
- Bryman, A. (2015). *Social research methods* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press Inc.
- Burns, E. (2024). Enhancing library communities through field-based projects. *Library Trends*, 72(4), 609–624. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lib.2024.a949573>
- Cash, P., Isaksson, O., Maier, A., & Summers, J. (2022). Sampling in design research: Eight key considerations. *Design Studies*, 78, 101077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.destud.2021.101077>
- Chaputula, A., H. (2014). Job prospects for Mzuzu University Library and Information Science Graduates. *New Library World*, 115(11/12), 571–587. <https://doi.org/10.1108/NLW-11-2013-0089>
- Chipeta, G., T., & Chawinga, W., T. (2018). A tracer study of Library and Information Science Graduates of Mzuzu University, Malawi. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*, 28(1), 33–47.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, k. (2018). *Research methods in Education* (8th ed.). Routledge.

- Cooper, L. Z. (2015). student reflections on an LIS internship from a service learning perspective supporting multiple learning theories. *Journal of Education for Library and Information Science*, 54(4).
- Creswell, J. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (4th ed.). Sage publications.
- Creswell, J., W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Darrin, T., & zubkov, p. (2023). *Quantitative research for practical theology. In quantitative research for practical theology*. Andrews University.
- Dondofema, J., Mwenje, J., & Musemwa, L. (2020). The industrial attachment programme - history, benefits, challenges and its adoption in Zimbabwe: A Review. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 6(3), 412–420.
<https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.522.2020.63.412.420>
- Duffus, O. (2017). Assessing UNC-Greensboro's reference interns Program: Enhancing the employability of LIS students. *College & Research Libraries News*, 78(5), 259.
<https://doi.org/10.5860/crln.78.5.259>
- Ellen, A., Rhodes. (2016). Literature reviews. *The Volta Review*, 111(1), 354–359.
<https://doi.org/10.17955/tvr.111.1.677>
- Fajonyomi, O. J., Omollo, D. A., & Fajonyom, M., G. (2024). reimagining internship in Library and Information Science Studies: Building a stronger entrepreneurship. *Journal of Education*, 45(1).

- Ghanad, A. (2023). An Overview of quantitative research methods. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 06(08). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v6-i8-52>
- Inyang, C., L., & Okwueze, E., A. (2024). Participation in students industrial work experience scheme and skills acquisition among Library and Information Science students in selected Universities in South-South, Nigeria. *Communicate. Journal of Library and Information Science*, 26(1), 347–355.
- Juznic, P., & Pymm, B. (2011). Students on placement: A comparative study. *New Library World*, 112(5/6), 248–260. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03074801111136284>
- Kavulya, J. M. (2017). Training of library and information science (LIS) professionals in Kenya: A needs assessment. *Library Review*, 56(3), 208–223. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00242530710735993>
- Khamis, Z. D., & Kaur, N. (2023). An overview and impact of the field attachment on prospected careers of the university's graduates in Zanzibar the case of the institute of public administration. *International Journal of Novel Research and Development*, 8(6), 2456–4184.
- Khan, A. (2022). Towards developing library and information science practicum supervision competency framework. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 54(2), 163–173. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000621997533>
- Kombo, D. K., & Tromp, A. D. L. (2016). *proposal and Thesis writing: An introduction*. Paulines publication Africa.

- Kuphanga, D. (2024). *Questionnaires in Research: Their Role, Advantages, and Main Aspects*.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15334.64325>
- Magara, E. (2025). Knowledge Transfer through Internship: The EASLIS Experience in Strengthening the Governance Decentralisation Programme in Uganda. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*, 21(1).
- Marciniak, J., Johnston, C. S., Steiner, R. S., & Hirschi, A. (2022). Career preparedness among Adolescents: A review of key components and directions for future research. *Journal of Career Development*, 49(1), 18–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845320943951>
- Maseka, A. (2020). *Evaluation of Library and Information science students' attachment programme: A case study of the University of Zambia*. [Thesis dissertation, University of Zambia]. <https://dspace.unza.zm/handle/123456789/6993>
- Mimansha, P., & Nitin, P. (2019). *Exploring research methodology: Review Article*. 6(3).
<http://www.ijrrjournal.com/>
- Mirza, C. (2023). *Ethical considerations in qualitative research: Summary guidelines for novice social science researchers*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370838199>
- Munyoro, P., K., & Mutula, S. (2016). Library and Information Science Education and Training and Employability Skills in Zimbabwe. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*, 26(2), 133–146.
- Mutsagondo, S. (2021). *Use and management of electronic mail in the central government of Zimbabwe* [Doctoral dissertation]. University of South Africa.

- Mzuzu University. (2025). *Academic programs*. <https://www.mzuni.ac.mw/programme-finder/undergraduate-programmes/>
- Mzuzu University. (2025, February 8). *About Mzuzu University*. <https://www.mzuni.ac.mw/about-us/>
- Norina, A., J., Sariwati, M., S., & Zurah, A. (2015). *Students' Practicum Performance of Industrial Internship Program*. 6th International Conference on University Learning and Teaching.
- Oben, A. I. (2021). Research instruments: A questionnaire and an interview guide used to investigate the implementation of higher education objectives and the attainment of Cameroon's vision 2035. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 8(7). <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v8i7.3808>
- Ojokuku, B., Y., Emeahara, E., N., Aboyade, M., A., & Israel, H., O.C. (2015). Influence of students' industrial work experience scheme on professional development of Library and Information Science Students In South-West, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Pandy, S., & Kumar, p. (2020). Perceived impact of LIS internship programme on personal and professional competencies of students of DLIS, Banaras Hindu University. *Journal of Indian Library Association*, 56(4).
- Pankajakshan, V., I., & Vidhukumar, k. (2020). Research designs-an overview. *Kerala Journal of Psychiatry*, 32(1). <https://doi.org/10.30834/kjp.32.1.2019.179>
- Sarkar, R. & Nand Kishore. (2024). Challenges and opportunities in Library and Information Science Education In West Bengal. *ShodhKosh: Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.29121/shodhkosh.v5.i1.2024.3341>

- Sathiyaseelan, M. (2015). Research instruments. *Indian Journal of Continuing Nursing Education*, 16(2), 57–60.
- Singh, A., & Masuku, M. (2016). Sampling techniques and determination of sample size in applied statistics research: Overview. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 2(11).
- Willie, M. M. (2024). Population and target population in research methodology. *Golden Ratio of Social Science and Education*, 4(1), 75–79. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grsse.v4i1.405>
- Wilson, M. (2016). Industrial attachment challenges: Lessons drawn from Gweru Polytechnic College in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 5(9), 37–42.
- Yesmin, S. (2025). Library and Information Science students' professional skills and personal competencies with internship effects: A case study of Bangladesh. *IFLA Journal*, 51(2), 242–254. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03400352241270880>